

DERIVATIONAL AND FUNCTIONAL AFFIXES

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Annotation. *If we describe a word as an autonomous unit of language in which a particular meaning is associated with a particular sound complex and which is capable of a particular grammatical employment and able to form a sentence by itself, we have the possibility to distinguish it from the other fundamental language unit, namely, the morpheme.*

A morpheme is also an association of a given meaning with a given sound pattern. But unlike a word it is not autonomous. Morphemes occur in speech only as constituent parts of words, not independently, although a word may consist of a single morpheme. Nor are they divisible into smaller meaningful units.

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Lexicology is primarily concerned with derivational affixes, the other group being the domain of grammarians. The derivational affixes in fact, as well as the whole problem of word-formation, form a boundary area between lexicology and grammar and are therefore studied in both.

Language being a system in which the elements of vocabulary and grammar are closely interrelated, our study of affixes cannot be complete without some discussion of the similarity and difference between derivational and functional morphemes.

The similarity is obvious as they are so often homonymous (for the most important cases of homonymy between derivational and functional affixes see p.18). Otherwise the two groups are essentially different because they render different types of meaning.

Functional affixes serve to convey grammatical meaning. They build different forms of one and the same word. A word form, or the form of a word, is defined as one of the different aspects a word may take as a result of inflection. Complete sets of all the various forms of a word when considered as inflectional patterns, such as declensions or conjugations, are termed paradigms. A paradigm has been defined in grammar as the system of grammatical forms characteristic of a word, e. g. *near, nearer, nearest; son, son's, sons, sons'*.

Derivational affixes serve to supply the stem with components of lexical and lexico-grammatical meaning, and thus form⁴ different words. One and the same lexico-grammatical meaning of the affix is sometimes accompanied by different combinations of various lexical meanings. Thus, the lexico-grammatical meaning supplied by the suffix - *y* consists in the ability to express the qualitative idea peculiar to adjectives and creates adjectives from noun stems. The lexical meanings of the same suffix are somewhat variegated: 'full of, as in *bushy* or *cloudy*, 'composed of, as in *stony*, 'having the quality of, as in *slangy*, 'resembling', as in *baggy*, 'covered with', as in *hairy* and some more. This suffix sometimes conveys emotional components of meaning.

E. g.: *My school reports used to say: "Not amenable to discipline; too fond of organising," which was only a kind way of saying: "Bossy."* (M. Dickens) *Bossy* not only means 'having the quality of a boss' or 'behaving like a boss'; it is also a derogatory word.

This fundamental difference in meaning and function of the two groups of affixes results in an interesting relationship: the presence of a derivational affix does not prevent a word from being equivalent to another word, in which this suffix is absent, so that they can be substituted for one another in context. The presence of a functional affix changes the distributional properties of a word so much that it can never be substituted for a simple word without violating grammatical standard. To see this point consider the following familiar quotation from Shakespeare:

Cowards die many times before their deaths; The valiant never taste of death but once.

Here no one-morpheme word can be substituted for the words *cowards*, *times* or *deaths* because the absence of a plural mark will make the sentence ungrammatical. The words containing derivational affixes can be substituted by morphologically different words, so that the derivative *valiant* can be substituted by a root word like *brave*. In a statement like *I wash my hands of the whole affair* (Du Maurier) the word *affair* may be replaced by the derivative *business* or by the simple word *thing* because their distributional properties are the same. It is, however, impossible to replace it by a word containing a functional affix (*affairs* or *things*), as this would require a change in the rest of the sentence.

The American structuralists B. Bloch and G. Trager formulate this point as follows: "A suffixal derivative is a two-morpheme word which is grammatically equivalent to (can be substituted for) any simple word in all the constructions where it occurs."¹

This rule is not to be taken as an absolutely rigid one because the word building potential and productivity of stems depend on several factors. Thus, no further addition of suffixes is possible after *-ness*, *-ity*, *-dom*, *-ship* and *-hood*.

A derivative is mostly capable of further derivation and is therefore homonymous to a stem. *Foolish*, for instance, is derived from the stem *fool* - and is homonymous to the stem *foolish* - occurring in the words *foolishness* and *foolishly*. Inflected words cease to be homonymous to stems. No further derivation is possible from the word form *fools*, where the stem *fool* - is followed by the functional affix *-s*. Inflected words are neither structurally nor functionally equivalent to the morphologically simple words belonging to the same part of speech. *Things* is different from *business* functionally, because these two words cannot occur in identical contexts, and structurally, because of the different character of their immediate constituents and different word-forming possibilities.

After having devoted special attention to the difference in semantic characteristics of various kinds of morphemes we notice that they are different positionally. A functional affix marks the word boundary, it can only follow the affix of derivation and come last, so that no further derivation is possible for a stem to which a functional affix is added. That is why functional affixes are called by E. Nida the outer formatives as contrasted to the inner formatives which is equivalent to our term derivational affixes.

It might be argued that the outer position of functional affixes is disproved by such examples as *the disableds*, *the unwanteds*. It must be noted, however, that in these words *-ed* is not a functional affix, it receives derivational force so that *the disableds* is not a form of the verb *to disable*, but a new word - a collective noun.

A word containing no outer formatives is, so to say, open, because it is homonymous to a stem and further derivational affixes may be added to it. Once we add an outer formative, no further derivation is possible. The form may be regarded as closed.

The semantic, functional and positional difference that has already been stated is supported by statistical properties and difference in valency (combining possibilities). Of the three main types of morphemes, namely roots, derivational affixes and functional affixes (formatives), the roots are by far the most numerous. There are many thousand roots in the English language; the derivational affixes, when listed, do not go beyond a few scores. The list given in "Chambers's Twentieth Century Dictionary" takes up five pages and a half, comprising all the detailed explanations of their origin and meaning, and even then the actual living suffixes are much fewer. As to the functional affixes there are hardly more than ten of them. Regular English verbs, for instance, have only four forms: *play*, *plays*, *played*, *playing*, as compared to the German verbs which have as many as sixteen.

The valency of these three groups of morphemes is naturally in inverse proportion to their number. Functional affixes can be appended, with a few exceptions, to any element belonging to the part of speech they serve. The regular correlation of singular and plural forms of nouns can serve to illustrate this point. Thus, *heart:: hearts*; *boy:: boys*, etc. The relics of archaic forms, such as *child:: children*, or foreign plurals like *criterion:: criteria* are very few in comparison with these.

Derivational affixes do not combine so freely and regularly. The suffix *-en* occurring in *golden* and *leaden* cannot be added to the root *steel-*. Nevertheless, as they serve to mark certain groups of

words, their correlations are never isolated and always contain more than two oppositions, e. g. *boy:: boyish, child:: childish, book:: bookish, gold:: golden, lead:: leaden, wood:: wooden*. The valency of roots is of a very different order and the oppositions may be sometimes isolated. It is for instance difficult to find another pair with the root *heart* and the same relationship as in *heart:: sweetheart*.

Knowing the plural functional suffix - *s* we know how the countable nouns are inflected. The probability of a mistake is not great.

With derivational affixes the situation is much more intricate. Knowing, for instance, the complete list of affixes of feminisation, i. e. formation of feminine nouns from the stems of masculine ones by adding a characteristic suffix, we shall be able to recognise a new word if we know the root. This knowledge, however, will not enable us to construct words acceptable for English vocabulary, because derivational affixes are attached to their particular stems in a haphazard and unpredictable manner. Why, for instance, is it impossible to call a lady-guest - *a guestess* on the pattern of *host:: hostess*? Note also: *lion:: lioness, tiger:: tigress*, but *bear:: she-bear, elephant:: she-elephant, wolf:: she-wolf*; very often the correlation is assured by suppletion, therefore we have *boar:: sow, buck:: doe, bull:: cow, cock:: hen, ram:: ewe*.

Similarly in toponymy: the inhabitant of London is called *a Londoner*, the inhabitant of Moscow is *a Muscovite*, of Vienna - *a Viennese*, of Athens - *an Athenian*.

On the whole this state of things is more or less common to many languages; but English has stricter constraints in this respect than, for example, Russian; indeed the range of possibilities in English is very narrow. Russian not only possesses a greater number of diminutive affixes but can add many of them to the same stem: *мальчик, мальчишка, мальчишечка, мальчонка, мальчуган, мальчугайка*. Nothing of the kind is possible for the English noun stem *boy*. With the noun stem *girl* the diminutive - *ie* can be added but not - *ette*, - *let*, - *kin* / - *kins*. The same holds true even if the corresponding noun stems have much in common: a short lecture is *a lecturette* but a small picture is never called *a picturette*. The probability that a given stem will combine with a given affix is thus not easily established.

To sum up: derivational and functional morphemes may happen to be identical in sound form, but they are substantially different in meaning, function, valency, statistical characteristics and structural properties.

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